

- The Social Media effect on externalizing feelings and prioritizing them over facts.
- [MESS0031: POS Wave of Propaganda](#)

MESS 0043

MIMS 2.84: How - after the religion to Authority and the pure destruction of War - collectivism is the most insidious and dangerous anti-MIMS of all; aka how False Yin (toxic feminism) is destroying the world in ways that even False Yang (toxic masculism) never did or could.

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February 2023

Best Viewed at: <https://bit.ly/3JD3Cp9>

ABSTRACT

Collectivism (Marxist or otherwise) is a social pathogen, which results in the creation of POS Supremes and Simplices on the order of millions, yearly. By encouraging the lowest common denominator in people, attributing it to grassroots this, or democratic that, covering up for a shallow identitarian sociopolitical agenda, society and the social contract degenerates. The Degenerates ruin society for no particular benefit of a subset of powerful POS elites. But in all reality, this paper isn't meant for these self-absorbed "Social Justice" types, but for serious classic liberals and paleoconservatives who wish for a solution that is anti-collectivist, and full of the promise of the mimsical "American (or other Western) Dream." Stay tuned for a plethora of links and "facts not caring about your feelings" moments, and a Reference Section so beefy, you'll think it needs Guile's Theme Song.¹

Keywords: POS Theory - Ayn Rand - welfare - socialism - patriotism - Ben Shapiro - Toxic Feminism

¹ [Guile's Theme Goes with Everything \(world's most epic handshake\)](#)

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Collectivism, as explained by Ayn Rand

The root of POS Theory² is that the “looters,” “moochers,” and “mystics” are those whose very basic philosophy is anti-science, anti-engineering/solutions, and anti-mimsical³. Their basic philosophy is in a lack of work, which is packaged (as any Marxist related philosophy would be) in social collection: shared workload, shared compensation, shared real estate, shared everything except (as you might guess) responsibility and freedom.

Among the looters and moochers is a general sense of pointless hunger. They are fed but unhappy, and therefore restless, whiney and despondent. But the hunger comes from a civilization generated and related malaise of “I need more” but without explanation. Without a strong mimsical lifestyle⁴ or a spiritual core as its strength, there will be a tendency to meander into any one of five, potentially deadly and difficult paths:

1. Radical religion or cultism.
2. Tribalistic obsession (as opposed to a healthy asceticism).
3. Hyper materialism, and rampant consumerism.
4. Militant expressionism (this explains a lot of the mass shootings we see now).
5. Pure downward spiral: drugs, homelessness, whoring, criminality, radicalization, gangs, etc.

As for the mystics, they are only happy if their anti-mimsical philosophies, like Big Bang, Darwinian evolution (or particularly the anthropological explanation it created), and Dark Universes⁵, etc. lead to mass confusion, distortion of reality and, ultimately, power for *them*, and disempowerment for not only their enemies, but Truth(ers) and the common man or family. Patriots and nationalists alike become an enemy of ‘convenience.’

The other part of POS Theory is based on Change Theory⁶. Steps in the evolution of new endeavors:

1. Great men (and unique women) create and pioneer new things.
2. They and good people build things up.
3. They hand it off to the middle managers.
4. The looters and moochers begin, through envy and “hook, nook, and crook,” to demand more and more of their “fair share” and “equity” in something that was already others’ actual equity built.
5. As time passes, more events alter the scenario. Eventually the original city, project, business, building, infrastructure, idea, whatever, is hollowed out.
6. The original creators and their ancestors who care the most - the Dagneys - are driven out, even as the Great men and women who carry the world, the John Galts, give up and move onto other things.
7. If this is a country or empire, it collapses, and things start over again as room is made by the demands of good people, for the great people to “fix things,” and they are demanded to do so. Great people do this because they are great. Good people do it because they are good but hope their kids will be capable of one day being moochers or great people.
8. As time goes on in the cycle we know two things:
 - a. Each generation is ignorant⁷ (and distrusted by the elder one) and needs to be re-re-re-taught history⁸ and wisdom.

² [MESS0013: the POS and Change crossing](#)

³ le - disastrous to life and environment. See: [MESS 1.0 and Double Layer Economics](#)

⁴ In Chinese, Yang Sheng “Nourishing Life” [YANG SHENG 養生 NOURISHING LIFE | Monkey Press](#)

⁵ [Dark Matter Scatter](#) & [Dark Matter Dine & Dash](#)

⁶ [MESS0006: POS Theory Grows Because Agenda](#)

⁷ [Renewable Ignorance](#)

⁸ [Why Are So Many Millennials Ignorant Anti-Americans?](#)

- b. Each passage of generation in a grand cycle, more moochers are born and the POS:good:great ratio increases and increases, until you never see the enemies around you.

Collectivism, as seen from this perspective, is not just a disease. It is a disease of innocence, ignorance (nescience even), which presents a social and national security threat through its insidious lies and promises. The promises, once made cannot be taken back; and the lies, once shared, get re-shared at accelerated rates, contrary to facts⁹ and historical evidence. It's one long example of "we've never had *real* communism," despite 100 years of failed communist and socialist states¹⁰, their environmental destruction¹¹, and genocides¹². We don't even talk about the collectivist failings at Jamestown¹³ and Plymouth Rock¹⁴, anymore. Instead the socialists have turned the failure of the communal pot and commune style religious cults of the pioneers¹⁵, into a story about English greed and bloodthirstiness¹⁶, and a story where farmers mysteriously didn't know how to farm, and they were also greedy for indian land. In other words: it wasn't the fault of the socialist system, it is the fault of innovators who were all the 'bad' capitalist and/or rugged-individualist things: greedy, aggressive, domineering, power obsessed, cruel, etc.

The POS explanation of the world is a form of "I'm not what I project onto you, I'm the good guy!"¹⁷

But in fact, like all abusers, they project the truth of themselves *onto* the better, more productive, happier, more spiritually grounded, calm and assertive people from a place of **codependent insecurity**. And when they are unable to get good people to believe them, they whine and modify 'studies'¹⁸ or even language/definitions to reflect their ideas¹⁹, in the form of lying propaganda²⁰. When they get traction, the only productivity they seem to accelerate in, is making unreasonable demands, and aggressive tactics, like rioting²¹, looting²², and POS policies²³. When they want a new racist policy, they claim the system is racist²⁴, and then demand a change, like Critical Theories²⁵, and Critical Race Theory²⁶. Then, when they feel insecure, they claim the alpha groups of males and females are the insecure ones, hence "White Fragility."²⁷

It's a technique called gaslighting²⁸, and it's actually shockingly effective because good people are empathetic, compassionate, tolerant, and *overly* accepting. It's a technique narcissists, sociopaths, dark

⁹ [FACTS DON'T CARE ABOUT YOUR FEELINGS: Speech is not violence](#)

¹⁰ [List of socialist states - Wikipedia](#)

¹¹ [Communism and the environment \(Journal Article\) | OSTI.GOV](#)

¹² [Mass killings under communist regimes - Wikipedia](#)

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Crimes_against_humanity_under_communist_regimes

¹³ "Within days of landing, the colonists were attacked by Powhatan Indians. The newcomers spent the next few weeks working to "bear and plant palisades" for a wooden fort. Three contemporary accounts and a sketch of the fort agree that its walls formed a triangle around a storehouse, church, and a number of houses" [History of Jamestown](#)

¹⁴ [The First Thanksgiving: What Really Happened](#)

¹⁵ [THE PILGRIMS' "FIRST THANKSGIVING" WAS NOT THE ONE WE REMEMBER | Faith and History](#)

¹⁶ As per Disney's "Pocahontas" lies.

¹⁷ ['Are we the Baddies?' Mitchell and Webb Funny Nazi Scetch](#)

¹⁸ [Hoaxers Slip Breastaurants and Dog-Park Sex Into Journals - The New York Times](#)

¹⁹ [UNDERCOVER: Crowder Infiltrates "FAT STUDIES" Conference | Louder with Crowder](#)

²⁰ [MESS0031: POS Wave of Propaganda](#)

²¹ [2020 George Floyd / Black Lives Matter Protests Map](#)

²² [Demonstrations and Political Violence in America: New Data for Summer 2020](#)

²³ [Higgins: Democrats' Push to Defund Police Caused Crime to Spike](#)

²⁴ [Black lives matter: On the denial of systemic racism, White liberals, and polite racism](#)

²⁵ [The Uniqueness of Western Civilization \(Studies in Critical Social Sciences, 28\): 9789004232761: Duchesne](#)

²⁶ [What is critical race theory and why are states banning it?](#)

²⁷ ['Woke Racism' tackles anti-racism, performative action and its effect on Black Americans](#)

²⁸ [Gaslighting - Wikipedia](#)

empaths²⁹, and even psychopaths use to get whatever they want through manipulation. That is why, at the top of the collectivist morasse, the dung heap of humanity, the piles of lost souls, will be a cult leader, or shady (even murderous) politician³⁰, a technocrat oligarch with delusions of grandeur (like Bill Gates), or a celebrity who can command legions of support through unearned admiration³¹ and fame³², etc.

Collectivism as a Means of Theft of Energy, Resources, and a method of Social Attack

Good people these days are perplexed and shocked, confused and bothered by the illegal, reprehensible actions of Black Lives Matter^{® 33}, Antifa³⁴, and many other groups of people who seem to be unemployed, useless as an anus on an elbow, and allowed (for reasons unknown, or political POS) to commit crimes, up to and including murder, with seemingly little consequence. Then, when heroes like Kyle Rittenhouse defend life³⁵ and family property with American values³⁶ and God-given rights³⁷, the POS system attacks them and their rights³⁸, instead of punishing the POS³⁹ and the dregs of society⁴⁰.

Now, the POS behavior of George Floyd⁴¹ does not excuse the manslaughter by the police. But instead of a trumped up political charge to one cop, it's clear that all four cops deserve manslaughter, and also that Floyd earned his death since he died not of asphyxiation, but of shock related to drug use⁴², stemming from criminal and disorderly behavior. But the worship of him is clearly a problem, and God does not appear amused⁴³.

But more important than (not lives but) the destruction of property is the destruction a society faces when - in the name of "a bleeding heart" - millions, or tens of millions of people; hundreds of millions worldwide; become absolutely useless and unproductive. Idleness and unemployment leads to a diminution of human energy⁴⁴ and momentum. Eventually the morass of weak economics devolves into full blown Mass Formation Psychosis⁴⁵, and this is a planned demolition which the Soviet KGB understood to actually be a mechanism of attack, called the four stages of revolution. Yuri Bezmenov explains⁴⁶:

1. Demoralisation
 - a. Both, literally in the form of eliminating a society's morals (hence the "child friendly drag queen shows")

"He was instructed by the KGB to not bother the 'political prostitutes' but instead surround

²⁹ [Dark Empath: A Dangerous Personality Type | Nobu Blog](#)

³⁰ Eg. Clintons, Bushes, Obama, Biden, etc.

³¹ <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/0033294119836765>

³² [Accidentally famous: The psychology of going viral | CNN](#)

³³ [BLM Is in Trouble, but Still Making Our Lives Worse | The Heritage Foundation](#)

³⁴ [Antifa—Background](#)

³⁵ [Rittenhouse: 'I didn't do anything wrong. I defended myself' | AP News](#)

³⁶ [Amazon.com: How to Destroy America in Three Easy Steps \(Audible Audio Edition\)](#)

³⁷ [God-given | definition in the Cambridge English Dictionary](#)

³⁸ <https://www.hawaiireporter.com/police-prosecutor-lawmakers-target-owners-of-firearms-second-amendment/>

³⁹ [Prosecutors dismiss looting, rioting charges against hundreds of protesters across U.S. - Washington Times](#)

⁴⁰ <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-11199697/Mob-homeless-San-Francisco-drug-addicts-brawling-sidewalk.html>

⁴¹ [Did George Floyd have a criminal past and what were his previous convictions? | The Sun](#)

⁴² [Lieutenant: Officers Should Have Intervened in Floyd Killing](#)

⁴³ [George Floyd Mural Struck By Lightning In Toledo, Ohio - CBS Minnesota](#)

⁴⁴ [The Problem of Increasing Human Energy](#)

⁴⁵ [What Is Mass Formation Psychosis? Robert Malone Makes Unfounded Covid-19 Vaccine Claims On Joe Rogan Show](#)

⁴⁶ [FULL INTERVIEW with Yuri Bezmenov: The Four Stages of Ideological Subversion \(1984\)](#)

himself with large conservative media persons, rich filmmakers, academicians, and cynical egocentric people. According to Benzmenov, the potential recruits and reputable people in the eyes of the KGB were narcissistic, greedy, morally devoid individuals who can help destabilise their country of origin. Citing the example of the United States, he stated that the KGB recruited professors and civil rights defenders to subvert and destabilise the country. "When their job is completed, they are not needed anymore. They know too much. Some (recruits) get offended when Marxists-Leninists come to power because they hoped they would come to power. That will never happen. They will be lined up against the wall and shot," he [Yuri] remarked."⁴⁷

- b. And in the literal morale and confidence (even belief in) the social fabric/contract and country (and tis founding fathers, documents, culture, and belief system, even religious validation).
2. Destabilization - 2012-current
3. Crisis - eg. 9/11, COVID-19, the "Space Pearl Harbor"⁴⁸
4. Normalization - where we are moving now; a place the POS Supremes feel they can control a critical mass of morass.

The theft of social economy and energy is not nearly as insidious, and (mutually) destructive, however, as the factual vampyrism of mental energies. When people think about nothing but gender, genitalia, sexual perversion, worry about why there is no one protecting them⁴⁹, or whether or not the police are incredibly racist or just a little (they are not⁵⁰), and to debate [endlessly] with one another about how a little, or more, restriction of freedom of speech/expression and gun control etc. are necessary. And this waste of mental energy disrupts an already accelerated deterioration of core strength of a society in a philosophical sense, away from enlightened STEMM and towards weaker, less mimsical philosophies:

- Tribalism
- Religious fanaticism
- Pure mysticism (without empirical basis)
- Numerology
- Obsessionism
- Dionysianism⁵¹
- Etc.

⁴⁷ [Former KGB agent Yuri Bezmenov exposes the four stages of a Communist takeover of a country in rare 1984 interview](#)

⁴⁸ [Why the US is risking a Pearl Harbor in space](#)

⁴⁹ Hint: it's the REAL System Racism: [MESS0032: POS Politics: Conservatives Systemic Racism Democrat Party](#)

⁵⁰ [Cops and Blacks - What Liberals won't Hear](#)

⁵¹ [Ferris Wheels and the Dionysian Irony](#)

Toxic Feminism; scourge of birth rates and worse...

Just as there is no toxic masculinity, there is no toxic femininity. Masculine and feminine traits (unlike gender) exist on a spectrum, and that spectrum is not controlled by the person at first, although they will modify it willfully with drugs and more. However, like any ism, and like anything according to POS Theory (and depending on the core strength and greatness of the founders, their ideals, and the idea itself) it can happen shortly or over a long period of time.

Feminism began (in its first wave) as the women's suffrage movement⁵². The best part of it probably died with women signing polls on the streets (as part of a social joke orchestrated by hacktivist POS Jimmy Kimmel) to "end women's suffrage"⁵³; preying upon the ignorance of modern women, who know little of the suffering of women in the 1800s, nor of the English language.

While hilarious, it was a sign of things to come as the "third wave" which was obsessed with women "getting their due" in the boardroom and "Breaking the Glass Ceiling" began to turn greedy. Unfortunately, the rhetoric never equalized the way the Truth did. Women have an income disparity⁵⁴, not a wage disparity⁵⁵, and in fact in many important regards we have passed parity⁵⁶. Women have, instead of a lack of equality, an unreasonable sense of victimization while they have an over parity in legal protections, and a defacto privilege to commit murder⁵⁷.

The women's movement has made women, and doctors, into participants in a genocide and then, a part of the Human Flesh Industry in general⁵⁸. Many are unwilling participants. But those who are, seem divided into some who feel guilty and want to acquiesce to this special right... which doesn't exist in liberalism, and only does exist because of a general Socialist plan to depopulate: blacks and minorities, Americans, the West, and really anyone who isn't part of the collectivist gestalt.

However, the unspoken of eugenicide is still well publicized as a failure of femininity, especially while we see "Karens" and others, go forward and amplify the issue with perceived loud mouths. More and more women *do not* identify themselves (thankfully) as feminist. While there are a few "Men's Rights Activists"⁵⁹ and a growing plethora of (incel or not) "MGTOWs"⁶⁰ the reality is there never has been a meaningful masculinist movement. But when so many people of both genders have devoted themselves to the radicalization and promotion of only one pole of the dipole, this has been a problem resulting in **generations of immoral and decadent, lazy, selfish, and frankly stupid as the day is long imbeciles**.

Incels⁶¹ aren't much of a threat, in the grand scheme of things. Much ado about them has been blamed on them desiring to rape women⁶². Little has been said, socially or elsewhere, about the rising and honestly

⁵² [The Women's Rights Movement, 1848-1917 | US House of Representatives: History, Art & Archives](#)

⁵³ [Man Show S1E01 "Stop Womens' Suffrage" Skit](#)

⁵⁴ Stemming from life and reproduction choices. [Median income for women is \\$14,900 less than that of men - USAFacts](#)

⁵⁵ [Harvard Study: "Gender Wage Gap" Explained Entirely by Work Choices of Men and Women - Foundation for Economic Education](#)

⁵⁶ [Percentage of the U.S. population with a college degree by gender 1940-2021 | Statista](#)

⁵⁷ [POS 1.01 Roe v Wade, Abortion](#)

⁵⁸ [The Human Meat Market | Freedom and Citizenship](#)

⁵⁹ [Feminism's Purity Wars](#); by the way, look at all the blatant misanthropy in the Google result searching "Men's Rights Activism" Apparently, men wanting to be treated well in law, family court, and divorce is teh same as hating women. Weird how that propaganda happens. As a male victim of Family Court sexism, and defacto shady activities being unpunished, the author has two middle fingers to give to the Southern Poverty Law Center (on lots of issues).

⁶⁰ Men Going Their Own Way; not a movement the author supports; it is full is plenty of misogyny. MRA often overlays with MGTOW, and it can be very unhealthy.

⁶¹ Involuntary Celibates (usually male).

⁶² [The online incel movement is getting more violent and extreme, report says](#)

weird fact that a majority of women harbor rape fetishes⁶³! There is much biology and relation to the socialization axis that science has shown and revealed⁶⁴. The modern feminist movement, the so-called fourth wave, has adherents attack second wave ideals and even the idea of “a woman”⁶⁵ as a distinct (and obviously scientific⁶⁶) thing. So much so that radical counter-culturists to this movement, called TERFs⁶⁷ have arisen to combat the fourth wave from “within” the feminist movement!⁶⁸

But the Truth, beyond all truths, is that all of this is the same mere [meta]physics that belies the issues of toxic masculism, and hyper-masculinity⁶⁹ (machismo): False Yin and False Yang⁷⁰ are betrayers of the dipole, and they abuse and [de]generate one another in an endless rotation. The poles do not stop existing. They simply rotate in a way that is now destructive, particularly to families, children, and society. But, given time, any wave of false yin or yang can destroy a society.

The difference here, is that though science shows us that fathers are the most important measure⁷¹ in a child’s future to avoid the fifth fate of the despondents listed above, especially prison time, we harbor a social *assumption* that mothers are more important⁷². In child-rearing, yes; but in adult-rearing, absolutely not. Moreover, we assert that *feminine* ideals are better for child development; eg. conflict resolution, discipline and punishment, reward in sport situations, etc. However, and barnone, the greatest purveyors of infanticide (without abortion as a cause), are mothers of very young children⁷³. And, then you get into the POS level of things where toxic feminists even have abortions just because their baby is male⁷⁴, or white⁷⁵, etc. These are unhinged young women, impressionable to the HFI propaganda (particularly of the racist Sanger’s⁷⁶ Planned Parenthood⁷⁷, which genocides black babies at a more than 3:1 rate as compared to white babies⁷⁸). When young women see the procedure⁷⁹ and hear the stories of real women⁸⁰, and survivors (which they usually do not know even exist), they almost always change their opinions on the spot. Some, however, radicalized

⁶³ More than 60% <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/all-about-sex/201508/why-do-women-have-rape-fantasies>
[The nature of women's rape fantasies: an analysis of prevalence, frequency, and contents](#)

⁶⁴ Jordan Peterson tells the real facts about Gender Equality and Gender Differences

⁶⁵ <https://www.openglobalrights.org/under-attack-from-all-sides-where-does-feminism-go-next/>

⁶⁶ le - “XX” chromosomes.

⁶⁷ Trans Exclusionary Radical Feminists

⁶⁸ LOL: [Feminist Attacks on Feminisms: Patriarchy's Prodigal Daughters](#) >> even if feminists critique it, it’s a man’s fault!

Meanwhile: [Why Are Attacks on Conservative Women Given Just a Shrug?](#)

⁶⁹ [Boxing Out Hyper-Masculinity](#)

⁷⁰ As per Dragongate/Quanzhen teachings of Liu Yiming [The Taoist I-Ching - tr. Thomas Cleary.pdf](#)

⁷¹ [Fathers' Involvement With Their Children: United States, 2006–2010](#) & [Father Absence Statistics](#)

⁷² Oh, the misandry! [Why are mothers better parents than fathers? Part I | Psychology Today](#)

⁷³ Try finding a simple article about the gender of neonatal homicide. Plenty of articles on the gender of the victims; or about how men commit more murders over age 5. Plenty of cross results about men and sexual assault... curious how there just isn’t a lot of information at the top of the results... Unless, of course you know that among women, who perform infanticide at roughly 5 times the rate of men, there is also a dramatic, many times difference between white and African American mothers, who commit by far the most infanticide and filicide (up to age 5). It’s almost like the collectivists don’t want the public to know this. It’s easier to find studies about infanticide among foreign countries, South Africa, or among mammals than answer the simple question of infanticide rate differences with fathers and mothers. [Infanticide and Neonaticide: A Review of 40 Years of Research Literature on Incidence and Causes](#)

⁷⁴ ['Feminist' says she aborted baby because it was a boy | Metro News](#)

⁷⁵ [Rabid Feminists are Gleefully Writing About Aborting Baby Boys...Because They're Boys](#)

⁷⁶ [Remove statues of Margaret Sanger, Planned Parenthood founder tied to eugenics and racism](#)

⁷⁷ [The Difference One Racist Made: Margaret Sanger's World](#)

⁷⁸ [Abortion Disproportionately Targets Black Babies: CDC: 74% of Abortions in Mississippi Were Performed on Black Mothers | CNSNews](#)

⁷⁹ After seeing abortion video people change there minds

⁸⁰ Rosaria Butterfield | How Psalm 102 Changed My Mind About Abortion

'It was devastating': Women describe emotional toll, journey of their abortions | ABCNL

beyond easy repair, continue to tout “Women’s rights” to murder, which again doesn’t exist but is expected as a form of recompensatory justice⁸¹ and equality for a series of atrocities⁸² and historical distortions **they also never personally experienced.**⁸³

Are these deranged people, again mostly young and/or sexually destitute women, usually Godless women, angry? Yes, they are. They do not know how to rationalize or deal with their anger in a constructive manner.⁸⁴ Their minds are obsessed with random victimization situations, such as hating metal poles⁸⁵, throwing trash cans⁸⁶ that represent the patriarchy (somehow), or seeing racist banana peels in trees⁸⁷. They have little value in the form of discourse⁸⁸, and cannot debate⁸⁹, so they screech⁹⁰ or yell⁹¹, or chant mindless hive-mind drive!⁹². Sometimes even about Israel and Palestine⁹³, which they know nothing about, either. But can they actually explain anything in a copacetic means, in the face of data, and evidence, once exposed? Not so far⁹⁴. There is, however, plenty of energy to go back to screeching, acting ridiculous, demanding vanity moments like social media attention, television time, and other ways to demonstrate their unhinged mental illnesses publicly. No one, not even their allies would let them watch their children or nieces and nephews. But for some reason it makes sense to allow them to screech wide-eyed on TV⁹⁵, rambling nonsense about topics they have little expertise in, and certainly little to no value in providing solutions for⁹⁶. In some cases, they screech their way into ludicrous positions, such as being morbidly obese experts in public health, or “first female” coaches in male sports while being fat, short, and generally incapable of winning a single solo match in any sport whatsoever.

⁸¹ [Feminism and Abortion | History Today](#)

Contrast with: [The Feminist Case Against Abortion](#)

⁸² [HISTORY OF ABORTION](#) “Over several centuries and in different cultures, there is a rich history of women helping each other to abort. Until the late 1800s, women healers in Western Europe and the U.S. provided abortions and trained other women to do so, without legal prohibitions”

So murder of the innocent is a “Rich history”, and if it’s an ancient institution of barbarism it’s “Rich.” So is slavery also a “rich history”? Do collectivists even think before writing this stuff?!

⁸³ Also: lies about rape statistics are difficult to correct when one side is always repeating in a screeching fashion the same wrong rhetoric.

⁸⁴ They need to take martial arts for five years.

⁸⁵ Until I find that video again, enjoy: [KAREN METAL](#)

⁸⁶ [Screaming college girl throws METAL trash can!!](#)

⁸⁷ [Discarded Banana Peel Causes Racial Hysteria at Ole Miss](#)

⁸⁸ [7 Things Feminists Hate to Hear And Absolutely Can't Talk About | Thought Catalog](#)

⁸⁹ [Peterson, McGregor, Badham share debate on gender, feminism | Q&A](#)

Goog God, they sound better when they stop, and re-evaluate their tactics...

[MEETING THE ENEMY A feminist comes to terms with the Men's Rights movement | Cassie Jaye | TEDxMarin](#)

⁹⁰ [WHO IS BIG RED? - The Story of Chanty Binx](#)

⁹¹ [FEMINIST vs DAD JOKES - The Chronicles of Hugh Mungus](#)

⁹² [Big Red: The Feminist Mind](#)

⁹³ [How the Black Lives Matter movement relates to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict](#)

⁹⁴ [Jordan Peterson Calmly DISMANTLES Feminism In Front Of Two Feminists \[REACTION!!!\]](#)

⁹⁵ [IS THAT A MICROAGGRESSION??](#)

⁹⁶ Aside from rambling about gun control, Crazy Cathy turned out to be a kidnapping POS

[Ex-Fox News Regular 'Liberal Sherpa' Accused of Kidnapping, Exploiting Elderly Mother](#)

Triggered Feminist, meme factory	Big Red, not the smartest one.	Crazy Cathy, POS elder abuser
Triggly Puff wants "hate speech" off the campus, and will act like a baby to get it. Future welfare POS.	Smugglypuff, the POS face of "I thought I could lie right to the police and avoid jail"	That one POS with the look of a school shooter.

It has gotten to the point that women in power positions, which are all they crave because they do not want to be bricklayers⁹⁷, high wire engineers, or sewage specialists, make threats to officers of the law⁹⁸ (male or female, but especially against males) to abuse their positions⁹⁹. That isn't new. Men have abused power forever. But what is unique is how readily they get away with it¹⁰⁰, to promote and promulgate themselves, abuse and corruptions which lead to seriously sinister situations. Monsters like Hillary Clinton¹⁰¹ are not born in a vacuum. If the "patriarchy" was so hard to defeat, then it wouldn't have ended in two generations, women would still be scrubbing toilets. A real patriarchy like in India, there are "untouchables"¹⁰² after 10,000+ years! Rather, toxic feminism has done what the Chinese sciences have said it would do (Du¹⁰³/poison). False Yang burns and destroys outright through a flash of Raw Power¹⁰⁴.

⁹⁷ [Jordan Peterson Confronts Australian Politician on Gender Politics and Quotas | Q&A](#)

⁹⁸ [Policeman pulls over black woman and quickly discovers she is the state attorney | The Independent](#)

⁹⁹ [Black state attorney pulled over in awkward video says she wants to sit down and talk to police | The Independent](#)

¹⁰⁰ [Ocasio-Cortez, chief of staff illegally moved \\$885G in campaign contributions 'off the books,' FEC complaint alleges | Fox News](#)

¹⁰¹ [The Clinton kill list.](#)

¹⁰² [India's "Untouchables" Face Violence, Discrimination](#)

¹⁰³ [毒 Poison or cure? Traditional Chinese medicine shows that context can make all the difference](#)

¹⁰⁴ "Axioms of Power," Sf. R. Careaga

False yin consumes, disrupts, corrodes, and undermines... and it has led to a decay in marriage rates¹⁰⁵, birth rates¹⁰⁶, national security¹⁰⁷, national sanity, and actually national safety and happiness of women. Women, mostly, do not even like working for other women¹⁰⁸. And when given the chance to live as a man¹⁰⁹ they find out it isn't super easy, barely an inconvenience¹¹⁰.

The fault is NOT femininity. If anything, feminism has made femininity an endangered species and a deteriorated, (and among lonely men) highly desirable trait. The fault is **entirely in feminism**, and its POS pathway from the start of a real movement co-opted by racist, eugenicist POS (Sanger), and then passed down generation to generation (see: POS Theory above). It'd be almost the same thing with masculism, except more slavery and war. But misery of the two sexes, the destruction of children¹¹¹ and their identities¹¹², as part of a gross, Satanic Human Flesh Industry¹¹³, etc. is just as catastrophic, and maybe more sinister, than ages of warlords and bloodlust.

Another way of saying this is that Venetian Mental Disease is just as bad, and maybe has been more disruptive to girls and women, and to boys' views of women, than Martian Mental Disease. Both cataclysms were disruptive. But the

expectations on women are unreasonable, and also probably have resulted in more broken marriages, early and against the warnings of psychologists, divorce experts, and the Bible's teachings on God's expectations for a marriage, than adultery or physical abuse. When women suddenly swing into this Venetian "territorial goddess" mode, well... as they say... "Hell hath no fury like a woman scorned."

- ❖ Sex goddess
- ❖ Provider for all
- ❖ Creative nurturer and source of life
- ❖ Light reflecting giver of agriculture
- ❖ *Mysteriously bi-polar "bitch" that becomes a Medusa¹¹⁴ destroying lives (turning people to pillars)*

Figure 7 ([gif](#)) - Diana Destroys Ares (again)
Credit: Warner Bros/DC

¹⁰⁵ Thanks, feminism & collectivism in general: [Marriages and Divorces - Our World in Data](#)

¹⁰⁶ [Why Is the U.S. Birth Rate Declining? | PRB](#)

¹⁰⁷ Less kids, weaker pool: [Russian Army Ad Makes Woke US Army Ad Look Like a Joke for Kids #Shorts | DM CLIPS | Rubin Report - YouTube](#)

¹⁰⁸ [Why Women Don't Want a Female Boss](#)

¹⁰⁹ [Self-Made Man \(book\) - Wikipedia](#)

¹¹⁰ [Wednesday Pitch Meeting](#)

¹¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SLFGMwoQaCU>

¹¹² [Texas Supreme Court Rules Against Father Trying to Prevent Gender Transition of His Son - RedState](#)

¹¹³ [97305562-Corruption-The-Satanic-Drug-Cult-Network-and-Missing-Children-Vol-1-of-4.pdf](#)

[97305628-Corruption-The-Satanic-Drug-Cult-Network-and-Missing-Children-Vol-2-of-4.pdf](#)

[97305716-Corruption-The-Satanic-Drug-Cult-Network-and-Missing-Children-Vol-3-of-4.pdf](#)

[97305780-Corruption-The-Satanic-Drug-Cult-Network-and-Missing-Children-Vol-4-of-4.pdf](#)

¹¹⁴ How dare a man wink or be handsome, and interested in a woman! [#amazon | Medusa makes friends](#)

Well, actually, the author worries there is a worse fury coming in the next 20-30 years. The fury of young men, punishing women, because of how they've been treated, and deprived of ordinary rights, merely expressing their natural sides¹¹⁵ (like stoicism¹¹⁶, arguing¹¹⁷, comedy¹¹⁸, and competitive violence¹¹⁹, innovation¹²⁰ and ladder-climbing¹²¹). Them, being tired of a toxic, oppressive welfare¹²²/anti-male system¹²³ that tries to make them feel guilty for being male, while also targeting their testosterone¹²⁴ and minds for destruction¹²⁵. The author worries that the masculism backlash will exceed reasonability, be bloody, violent, and if not only political, religiously extreme, leading to a form of brutishness. It might be that the author's only solution he can provide at this time is the only one that won't be mutually destructive; particularly though for women and children.

A Sad, but Liberal Solution

Feminists have complained about male-created everything¹²⁶. Now that men have found the keys to engineering, math, and science, and women have had time to learn them¹²⁷... let them have a separate society, a pink society as it were. A pre-Venus terraforming culture, specifically for women to go to who do not want to be a part of the so-called "Patriarchy."

Let them control everything therein. Let them build and be responsible for EVERYTHING therein, including the sewage, electricity, brick-laying, etc., and find out what men have carried, since we left the caves, swamps, forests, and deserts to conquer disease and poverty and feudalism. Oh, and, of course, repugnant plunder economics, guided by self-centeredness and the religion of authority; rooted in "Divine right to rule." The latter, of course, is a gross misguided aspect stemming from misunderstanding and misinterpretation of what we've been through *which itself* was passed down as anthropomorphic knowledge, easily warped, misinterpreted, abused as a source of knowledge and power, and ultimately, an origin of war and destruction to men, women, and children everywhere.

Let them eat cake, and be thus equal in fact, and not only in *theme*.

Conclusions

Collectivism focuses on ridiculous ideals, which aren't actually that idealistic, utopian¹²⁸, or generous in spirit. For example, stealing one person's wealth to enhance that of many, is a violation of Justice. It cannot,

¹¹⁵ [How feminists developed 'toxic masculinity' – A Voice for Men](#)

¹¹⁶ [What Does It Mean For A Man To Be Stoic? | Men's Health](#)

¹¹⁷ [Men and Women Tend to Argue About Different Things, in Different Ways - The Atlantic](#)

¹¹⁸ [Men are funnier than women, study claims - BBC News](#)

¹¹⁹ [MESS0010: MIMS 2.81 - Violence as a MIMS](#) vs [Harmful masculinity and violence](#) < how is this helpful?

¹²⁰ [Why are most inventors men? | PBS NewsHour](#)

¹²¹ [When Climbing Corporate Ladder, Women Are as Competitive as Men: Study - A Woman's View | Healthcare for Women | Hickory, NC](#) So they say, but statistically women are less common to make it through this, because of child-rearing choices. It's a mass of numbers issue.

¹²² [Ghetto Baby Mama RESPONDS To Massive Backlash After Trashing Good Father For Feeding His Kid](#)

¹²³ Eg - Family court

¹²⁴ [Testosterone levels show steady decrease among young US men](#)

¹²⁵ [Is The Concept Of 'Toxic Masculinity' Unfair To Young Men? | Q&A](#) Of course it is. If we had a systemic commercialization and propaganda campaign attacking femininity and physical gender traits of young girls, this would be unfair and destructive to them. This isn't a debate. It's a fact.

¹²⁶ [Feminists Say Roofie-Detecting Nail Polish Is Actually Also Rape Culture | National Review](#) Imagine being this stupid.

¹²⁷ [Women Making Gains in STEM Occupations but Still Underrepresented](#)

¹²⁸ Unless you mean "no place."

therefore, create any form of “Social Justice.”¹²⁹ On the one hand you destroy justice, and on the other you destroy society when people stop working hard, trusting one another, or plain give up and go on welfare. Welfare increases criminality and dependency, corruption of society and government, and weakens people.

Take even socially accepted American collectivism. For example, people sing every year, Lennon’s “Imagine” song¹³⁰, at New Year’s Eve in New York City (hub of world capitalism). Why? It sounds beautiful. Feels hopeful. If by hopeful they mean opium-like, that’s true. Read the monstrosity of it in the first stanzas,

“Imagine there’s no heaven -What a horrifying concept for most people worldwide
It’s easy if you try;

No hell below us, Above us, only sky;

Imagine all the people, Livin’ for today Ah;

Imagine there’s no countries -by far most people identify with their own people in their own lands

It isn’t hard to do; Nothing to kill or die for

And no religion, too -Why not throw this into your Hellscape Utopia? Just violate all rights!!

Imagine all the people

Livin’ life in peace -What peace exists in a world where an eternal boot tells you you cannot be human?

I suppose his last name being a homophone for a major Bolshevik mass murderer¹³¹, is not necessarily an accident. Still, one has to love, somewhat, this level of idealism. It’s only really a problem when it goes from freedom of expression to religious or political extremism, and eventually to social movements that result in gulags¹³² for “reactionaries”¹³³ and a need to “retrain minds.”¹³⁴ When one presents a (1) **Clear** and (2) **Present Danger**¹³⁵ to others and society at large, one’s rights end (whatever one’s persuasion and identity), and enter the realm of “okay, you’re a problem, now.”

The POS collectivists have long ago now entered that realm. That’s what 2020 represented to the vast majority of western civilization. A POS Wave of fascism and “the Stupid.”¹³⁶ No one likes these people, not even each other¹³⁷. That’s something they are, generally speaking, too self-absorbed¹³⁸, loud-mouthed¹³⁹, and busy stuck in an ‘autistic’ Narcissistic mode¹⁴⁰, to pay attention to. That’s why, with healthy boundaries¹⁴¹, good,

¹²⁹ [▶ Stossel: Jordan Peterson vs. “Social Justice Warriors”](#)

¹³⁰ [▶ New Year 2023 New York Time Square Ball Drop | Chelsea Cutler "Imagine" | Countdown](#)

¹³¹ [Soviet Union - Lenin and the Bolsheviks | Britannica](#)

¹³² [The Gulag Archipelago in three volumes : Aleksandr Solzhenitsyn : Free Download, Borrow, and Streaming : Internet Archive](#)

¹³³ [Reactionary - Wikipedia](#)

¹³⁴ [▶ Jordan Peterson ORDERED to Reeducation Camp for Wrongthink | Guest: Sara Gonzales | Ep 739](#)

¹³⁵ [clear and present danger | Wex | US Law](#)

¹³⁶ [▶ CoNsErVaTiVes ArE MoRe eXTrEmE - DEBUNKED](#)

¹³⁷ [4 Reasons Some Women Hate Feminism \(And What They’re Missing\) - The Life of Science](#)

¹³⁸ [5 Narcissistic Symptoms Of ‘Social Justice Warriors’ | Evie Magazine](#)

¹³⁹ [Why are SJW/far-left opinions so loud?](#)

¹⁴⁰ [▶ "How dare you?" - Emotional Greta Thunberg attacks world leaders](#)

¹⁴¹ [Boundaries. Updated and Expanded Edition: When to Say Yes, How to Say No to Take Control of Your Life](#)

common, decent folk should learn to simply say “No.” Let woke agenda corporations fail¹⁴².¹⁴³ Let patriotic products soar¹⁴⁴. “The Salt Must Flow.”

Figure 8 - Mo'adib! ; credit: Dune/Universal

Figure 9 - “hOw DaRe YoU!” (gif) - the face and cry of unearned entitlement meeting Dunning-Kruger levels of incompetent, self-appointed expertise; credit: MyHeritage/KnowYourMeme

¹⁴² [These Media Stocks Have Fallen More than 50% This Year](#)

¹⁴³ [Facebook's \\$232 billion fall sets record for largest one-day value drop in stock market history](#)

¹⁴⁴ [Top Gun: Maverick Becomes 5th Highest-Grossing Domestic Film Ever](#) & [Top Gun: Maverick - Box Office Mojo](#)

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Ah, the Misogyny and Misanthropy of Hypocrisy

The following are actual products sold by feminists; please enjoy these toxic merch:

#1 search result for “feminist store merch”:

Probably still a man's fault.

That literally makes no sense

Ah, ye olde racist POS-POC

Literally no one:

Ah ye olde genitalia mutilation brigade:

Emphasis on the F word

You can smell the toxic pink hair and no deodorant from here.

And how, pray tell, do you intend to do that without violence?

Once again, logic fail. Shocker.

You said it, not me.

Literally it is homicide; is homicide healthcare? Love the communist symbolism, makes this straight-forward.

Actually ...

(1) Not be bleeding (2) while standing and peeing; so... not true.

What does that even mean?

Ah the fever dream

Less chocolate will help.

I'm rooting for a diabetes free America

Ah, ye olde double standards

Racism has its allies & frienemies

A surefire way to fail at parenting

Bear in mind the author didn't include every result; just examples of the most toxic and collectivist nonsense.